

Antagonistic Endophytic Bacteria as a Promising Source of Bioactive Secondary Metabolites

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ABSTRACT

The continuous demand for novel bioactive compounds has intensified the exploration of natural sources, particularly for applications in pharmaceuticals and agrochemicals. Among these, endophytic bacteria that reside asymptotically within plant tissues have emerged as a significant and underexplored reservoir of diverse bioactive secondary metabolites. The present study focuses on the isolation and characterization of antagonistic endophytic bacteria from *Abrus precatorius*. It is a medicinally important plant commonly known as Gunja, belonging to the family Fabaceae and is recognized for its broad spectrum of therapeutic properties. Endophytic bacterial isolates were obtained from leaf tissues of *Abrus precatorius* using standard surface sterilization and microbiological culturing techniques. Among the isolates obtained, two bacterial strains exhibited antagonistic relationship. They were identified as *Pseudomonas parafulva* and *Bacillus mycooides*. *Pseudomonas parafulva* exhibited significant antagonistic activity against *Bacillus mycooides*, as evidenced by inhibition of its growth in vitro. This antagonistic interaction suggests the production of bioactive secondary metabolites with potential antimicrobial properties. The findings highlight the role of endophytic bacteria associated with medicinal plants as promising candidates for the discovery of novel bioactive compounds. Overall, this study underscores the importance of bioprospecting endophytic bacterial communities from medicinal plants such as *Abrus precatorius* and supports their potential application in the development of new antimicrobial agents.

Keywords: Endophytes, *Abrus precatorius*, antagonistic, *Pseudomonas parafulva*, *Bacillus mycooides*.

INTRODUCTION

Abrus precatorius has been recognized since ancient times for its extensive therapeutic potential in traditional medicine systems (Boye et al., 2021). However, there remains a significant research gap regarding the isolation and characterization of endophytic bacteria associated with this plant. Various parts of *A. precatorius*, including its distinctive red-and-black seeds, leaves, and roots, have been widely utilized for medicinal purposes (Kirtikar & Basu, 1999; Nadkarni, 2007). Traditionally, the plant has been employed in the treatment of wounds, scratches, and sores caused by animals such as dogs, cats, and rodents, and in combination therapies for leukoderma, tetanus, and rabies

(Warrier et al., 1993). The leaves function as a nerve tonic and are applied to cuts, swellings, and oral ulcers, while roots are used for gonorrhoea, jaundice, and haemoglobinuria (Anamika et al., 2016). Seed oil has demonstrated antimicrobial properties (Aswin et al., 2022) and promotes hair growth, and powdered seeds are used in tuberculous swellings (Bhakta et al., 2010). Recent studies have further validated the pharmacological significance of *A. precatorius*. For instance, aqueous seed extracts have shown significant antioxidant, antiproliferative, and antiangiogenic activities, with potential inhibition of cancer-related pathways such as COX-2 (Kaur et al., 2024). Similarly, nanoconjugates synthesized from seed extracts have demonstrated enhanced anticancer efficacy and bioactivity, indicating promising applications in nanomedicine (Kaur, et al., 2023). These findings support earlier reports of its anticancer and antimicrobial potential.

In addition, contemporary research highlights the importance of endophytic microorganisms as sources of novel bioactive compounds, including antimicrobial and anticancer agents, particularly in medicinal plants (Tiwari et al., 2025; El-Zehery et al., 2024). Endophytes are increasingly recognized for producing secondary metabolites that contribute to host plant defence and therapeutic properties, reinforcing the need to explore endophytic diversity in *A. precatorius* (Parveen et al., 2025). *A. precatorius* is native to India, particularly in the Himalayan region up to altitudes of approximately 1,200 meters, but is now widely distributed across tropical regions, including southern India and Sri Lanka (Anamika et al., 2016 and Kirtikar & Basu, 1999). The growing body of recent research underscores its pharmacological relevance and highlights a critical research gap in exploring its endophytic microbiota for novel bioactive compounds. Endophytes are an endosymbiotic group of microorganisms that colonize in plants and can be readily isolated from any part of the host plant (Gouda et al., 2016). They act as reservoirs of novel versatile secondary metabolite, such as alkaloids, phenolic acids, quinones, steroids, saponins, tannins, and terpenoids. These compounds serve as a potential candidate for anti-microbial, anti-pesticide, anticancer and many more properties (Adeleke et al., 2021). While plant sources are being extensively explored for new chemical entities for therapeutic purposes, endophytic microbes also constitute an important source for drug discovery.

Endophytes exhibit diverse and dynamic interactions with their host plants, ranging from mutualistic to antagonistic associations (Archana et al. 2020). Dark septate endophytes (DSE), commonly found within root tissues, represent a distinct group of endophytic fungi characterized by melanized, septate hyphae. Endophytic microorganisms, including both fungi and bacteria, may colonize either below-ground tissues such as roots or above-ground parts such as stems and leaves. While many endophytes establish mutualistic relationships that enhance host fitness, others may shift toward parasitic behaviour depending on environmental and physiological conditions. Notably, these associations are generally asymptomatic and remain inconspicuous within host tissues (Zhang et al., 2019; Rai et al., 2021).

The interaction between endophytes and host plants is often described as a continuum, involving both mutualistic and antagonistic elements driven by mutual exploitation. Stable and highly integrated symbiotic relationships require a close alignment of morphological, physiological, and life-history traits between the host and the endophyte, enabling their coevolution and persistence (Saikkonen et al., 1998). However, disruption of this balance due to environmental stress or genetic factors can lead to a breakdown of symbiosis.

Recent studies have highlighted that host plants benefit significantly from endophytic associations, including enhanced resistance to herbivores and pathogens, improved tolerance to abiotic stresses such as drought and flooding, and increased ecological competitiveness (Yadav et al., 2019; Santoyo et al., 2021). In response, plants regulate endophyte colonization through various defence mechanisms, including the production of toxic secondary metabolites and activation of defence-related enzymes. Conversely, endophytes produce exoenzymes and bioactive compounds that facilitate host colonization and persistence within plant tissues (Rana et al., 2020).

The evolution of endophyte-plant symbiosis is a complex process influenced by multispecies interactions and environmental factors that shape the co-evolutionary dynamics of both partners (Saikkonen et al., 2004). These interactions ultimately confer ecological advantages to both host plants and endophytes, reinforcing their importance in plant

health and ecosystem functioning (Chitnis et al., 2020; Singh, 2024).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of Plant Samples

Healthy plant parts (roots, stems, and leaves) of *Abrus precatorius* were collected from an individual plant growing in the local region of Jethkheda, District Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India. The sampling site was located at geographic coordinates 20.189359° N latitude and 75.289758° E longitude (Khuldabad, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India) (Figure 1). Collected samples were placed in sterile polyethylene bags and transported to the laboratory under aseptic conditions. Samples were processed immediately upon arrival to minimize the risk of contamination.

2.2 Collection and analysis of Soil Sample

Soil samples were collected from the rhizosphere region of the plant using standard soil sampling procedures. Approximately 6 inches deep soil was collected after removing surface debris and plant residues using a sterile soil sampling tube. The collected soil was transferred into clean containers, homogenized thoroughly, and transported to the laboratory for further analysis. The samples were air-dried at room temperature, ground gently, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh to remove debris and obtain a uniform sample for analysis. Soil samples collected from the rhizosphere region of *Abrus precatorius* were analysed to determine their physicochemical properties. The samples were air-dried at room temperature, ground gently, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh to remove debris and obtain a uniform sample for analysis. All analyses were carried out following standard procedures recommended by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO).

2.2.1 Determination of Soil pH

Soil pH was measured using a digital pH meter following standard protocols of the Food and Agriculture Organization. A soil-water suspension was prepared in a 1:2.5 ratio (w/v), mixed thoroughly, and allowed to equilibrate. The pH of the supernatant was then recorded.

2.2.2 Electrical Conductivity (EC)

Electrical conductivity was determined using a conductivity meter to assess soluble salt content. The soil extract prepared for pH measurement was used,

and EC values were recorded at 25°C and expressed in mS/cm.

2.2.3 Organic Carbon (OC)

Organic carbon content was estimated by the Walkley-Black wet oxidation method. Soil samples were treated with potassium dichromate and concentrated sulfuric acid, followed by titration with ferrous ammonium sulfate. The percentage of organic carbon was calculated based on the amount of dichromate consumed.

2.2.4 Available Nitrogen (N)

Available nitrogen was determined using the alkaline permanganate method. Soil samples were digested with alkaline potassium permanganate, and the released ammonia was absorbed in boric acid and titrated with standard acid. Results were expressed in kg/ha.

2.2.5 Available Phosphorus (P)

Available phosphorus was estimated using the Olsen method. Soil samples were extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution, and the phosphorus content was determined colorimetrically using a spectrophotometer.

2.2.6 Available Potassium (K)

Available potassium was determined by extracting soil samples with neutral ammonium acetate solution. The potassium concentration in the extract was measured using a flame photometer and expressed in kg/ha.

2.3 Isolation of Endophytic Bacteria (Weber et al. Method)

Isolation of endophytic bacteria was carried out following the method described by Weber *et al.*, with slight modifications (Weber et. al 1999). Plant samples were initially washed under running tap water to remove adhering dust and debris, followed by rinsing with distilled water. The samples were then excised into smaller segments under aseptic conditions and subjected to surface sterilization. Surface sterilization was performed by sequential immersion of the plant segments in 70% (v/v) ethanol for 3 minutes, followed by 5% (w/v) sodium hypochlorite solution for 5 minutes, and again in 70% ethanol for 1 minute. After each step, the samples were rinsed thoroughly with sterile distilled water. This sterilization procedure was repeated twice to ensure complete removal of surface contaminants.

2.3.1 Sterility Test

To confirm the effectiveness of surface sterilization, a sterility check was performed. An aliquot (1 mL) of the final rinse water was spread onto nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. These plates served as controls, and the absence of microbial growth confirmed successful surface sterilization.

2.3.2 Isolation of Endophytic Bacteria

Surface-sterilized plant segments (leaves, stems, and roots) were aseptically placed onto nutrient agar plates and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. Plates showing no microbial growth in control (sterility test) were considered valid. Emerging bacterial colonies from the plant tissues were presumed to be endophytic and were further sub-cultured for subsequent characterization and analysis. All the isolates (as per fig. 3 and 4) were streaked on nutrient agar plates by making four sections, one colony on each section and incubated at room temperature for 24 hours.

2.4 Extraction of Secondary Metabolites Using Ethyl Acetate

Endophytic bacterial isolates exhibiting antimicrobial activity, particularly those producing yellow pigmented colonies with a clear zone of inhibition, were selected for secondary metabolite extraction. The selected colony was purified by streaking on nutrient agar plates using the four-quadrant streaking method and incubated at room temperature for 24 hours. A single isolated colony was then inoculated into 100 mL of sterile minimal media and incubated at room temperature for 5 days on a rotary shaker at 180 rpm to facilitate metabolite production. After incubation, the culture broth was centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 10 minutes to separate the bacterial cells from the culture supernatant. The supernatant (50 mL) was transferred to a separating funnel, and an equal volume of ethyl acetate was added. The mixture was vigorously shaken and allowed to stand for approximately 20 minutes to allow phase separation. Two distinct layers formed, and the upper organic layer (ethyl acetate phase) was carefully collected. The collected organic phase was subjected to evaporation to remove the solvent and obtain the crude extract containing secondary metabolites. After complete evaporation, the crude extract was dissolved in 1 mL of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and stored for further antimicrobial or biochemical analysis.

2.5 Molecular Analysis

2.5.1 DNA Extraction and PCR Amplification

The bacterial sample was subjected to genomic DNA extraction using the NucleoSpin Microbial DNA Kit according to the manufacturer's protocol. The quality and integrity of the extracted DNA were assessed by electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel and visualized under a UV transilluminator (HiMedia, India). The 16S rRNA gene fragment was amplified using universal primers 27F and 1492R. PCR amplification was performed under optimized thermal cycling conditions. The amplified products were resolved on 1.2% agarose gel, and a single discrete band corresponding to the expected size of the 16S rRNA gene fragment was observed.

2.5.2 Purification and Sequencing of PCR Products

The PCR amplicons were purified to remove residual primers, nucleotides, and other contaminants. Purified products were subjected to bidirectional sequencing using forward and reverse primers with the BigDye® Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (Applied Biosystems, USA). Sequencing reactions were performed on an ABI 3730xl Genetic Analyzer. Prior to sequencing, PCR products were enzymatically cleaned using Exonuclease I and Shrimp Alkaline Phosphatase to eliminate unincorporated nucleotides and primers. Sequencing products were further purified by ethanol precipitation and resuspended in Hi-Di formamide before analysis.

2.5.3 Sequence Alignment and Identification

The forward and reverse sequences obtained were assembled into a consensus sequence using BioEdit software. The resulting sequence was manually trimmed and edited to ensure accuracy. Sequence similarity searches were performed using the BLAST program against the NCBI GenBank database to identify closely related taxa. Multiple sequence alignment was carried out using ClustalW implemented in MEGA version 11. Species identification was based on maximum sequence similarity scores and alignment results.

2.5.4 Phylogenetic Analysis

Phylogenetic relationships were inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method implemented in MEGA 11 software. The robustness of the tree topology was evaluated using bootstrap analysis with 1,000 replicates. Branches with less than 50% bootstrap support were collapsed. Evolutionary distances were

computed using the p-distance method and expressed as the number of base substitutions per site. All ambiguous positions were removed using the pairwise deletion option. The final dataset comprised 1,282 nucleotide positions derived from 12 sequences. The resulting phylogenetic tree was used to determine the evolutionary relationships and confirm the taxonomic position of the isolate.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Collection and Documentation of Plant Sample

The plant sample of *Abrus precatorius* was successfully collected from Khuldabad, Aurangabad, Maharashtra, India (20.189359° N, 75.289758° E). The collected specimens were properly documented and preserved

as herbarium vouchers by pressing and drying between sheets of newspaper. Proper preservation ensures long-term storage and utility for future taxonomic and research purposes. The prepared herbarium specimens serve as a permanent record of the plant material used in this study (Figure 1).

3.2 Soil Analysis

Soil analysis was performed to evaluate the physicochemical properties of the rhizosphere soil, including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), organic carbon (OC), and essential nutrients such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K). These parameters provided insights into the environmental conditions supporting plant growth. The results of soil analysis are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1. Collection of plant specimen of *Abrus precatorius*

Table 1. Physicochemical analysis of rhizospheric soil of *Abrus precatorius* using standard Food and Agriculture Organization protocols.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Unit	Method (FAO)	Standard Range	Observed Value	Interpretation
1	pH (25°C)	—	FAO 2007	6.51–7.50	7.78	Slightly alkaline
2	Electrical Conductivity (EC, 25°C)	mS/cm	FAO 2007	0.01–1.00	0.078	Sufficient
3	Organic Carbon	%	FAO 2008	1.01–2.00	0.54	Low
4	Nitrogen (N)	kg/ha	FAO 2008	281–420	175.62	Low
5	Phosphorus (P)	kg/ha	FAO 2007	15–21	32.44	High
6	Potassium (K)	kg/ha	FAO 2008	151–240	504.0	High

3.3 Isolation of Endophytic Bacteria

3.3.1 Sterility Test

Surface sterilization of plant samples using the Weber et al. method was effective in eliminating epiphytic contaminants. No microbial growth was observed on control plates inoculated with the final rinse water, confirming successful sterilization. Distinct microbial growth was observed only around plant tissue segments, indicating the presence of true endophytes.

3.3.2 Isolation of Endophytic Bacteria

Surface-sterilized segments of leaves, stems, and roots were incubated on nutrient agar plates. Morphologically distinct bacterial colonies appeared surrounding the plant segments within 24–48 hours. A total of 17 endophytic bacterial isolates were obtained in pure form from 38 plant segments. Repetitive colonies were excluded to ensure diversity among isolates (Figure 3).

Figure 2. The endophytic bacteria isolated from plant specimen

Figure 3 and 4. The isolated pure endophytic bacteria from Abrus plant, and pure culture of *Bacillus mycoides*

Figure 5. Phylogenetic tree for identification of isolate exhibiting antimicrobial property

3.3.3 Purification of Isolates

All 17 isolates were purified using repeated streaking techniques and maintained as pure cultures. The isolates were labelled based on their source: A1–A4 (nodes), B1–B4 (leaves), and C1–C8 (roots). An additional isolate identified as *Bacillus mycoides* was designated as D and used as a test organism (Figures 3 and 4).

3.3.5 Phylogenetic Analysis

The phylogenetic analysis based on 16S rRNA gene sequencing revealed that the obtained isolate exhibiting antimicrobial property clustered within the genus *Pseudomonas*. In the constructed phylogenetic tree, the isolate showed close evolutionary proximity with *Pseudomonas parafulva* strain OsEp Plm. The clustering was supported by high bootstrap values

($\geq 99\%$), indicating strong confidence in the branching pattern. The isolate formed a distinct clade along with *Pseudomonas parafulva*, clearly separated from other closely related species such as *Pseudomonas fulva* and *Pseudomonas putida*. The high sequence similarity and robust phylogenetic placement confirm that the isolate belongs to *Pseudomonas parafulva*. Thus, based on molecular phylogenetic analysis, the isolate was successfully identified as *Pseudomonas parafulva*.

3.4 Extraction of Secondary Metabolites

Among the 17 isolates, a yellow pigmented colony (Identified as *Pseudomonas parafulva*) demonstrated inhibitory activity and was selected for secondary metabolite extraction. The metabolites were extracted using the ethyl acetate solvent extraction method. The crude extract was obtained after solvent evaporation and stored under cooled and light-protected conditions for further analysis (Figure 4).

Figure 6. Solvent extraction of secondary metabolites produced by *Pseudomonas parafulva*

Figure 7. Antimicrobial activity against *Salmonella typhi* (left) and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Control used was penicillin disc (10U)

3.5 Antimicrobial Activity

The extracted secondary metabolites from *Pseudomonas parafulva* was evaluated for antimicrobial activity against test organisms *Salmonella typhi*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus mycoides*. The results indicated that the extract exhibited significant antimicrobial activity only against *Bacillus mycoides*. In the disk diffusion assays, a clear zone of inhibition was observed against *Salmonella typhi* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, confirming the antimicrobial potential of the extracted secondary metabolites. The present study demonstrates that endophytic bacteria associated with *Abrus precatorius* represent a promising source of bioactive secondary metabolites with antimicrobial potential. *Pseudomonas parafulva* also exhibited notable antagonistic activity, particularly against *Bacillus mycoides* that itself was an endophytes from the same plant leaf. The extraction of secondary metabolites using ethyl acetate further validated that the antimicrobial activity was associated with diffusible bioactive compounds produced by the endophyte. These findings highlight the ecological significance of endophyte–host interactions, where endophytic bacteria contribute to host defence by producing antimicrobial metabolites. The selective activity observed in this study also suggests specificity in the mode of action of these compounds, indicating potential for targeted antimicrobial applications. Overall, this research supports the concept that antagonistic endophytic bacteria from medicinal plants are valuable reservoirs of novel bioactive compounds. Further studies involving molecular identification, purification, and characterization of these metabolites, along with evaluation against a broader range of pathogens, are necessary to explore their potential in pharmaceutical and biotechnological applications.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that endophytic bacteria associated with *Abrus precatorius* represent a promising source of bioactive secondary metabolites with antimicrobial potential. Among the isolates, *Pseudomonas parafulva* exhibited notable antagonistic activity, particularly against *Bacillus mycoides*, while no significant inhibition was observed against other tested pathogens. The extraction of secondary metabolites using ethyl acetate further validated that the antimicrobial activity was associated with

diffusible bioactive compounds produced by the endophyte. These findings highlight the ecological significance of endophyte–host interactions, where endophytic bacteria contribute to host defence by producing antimicrobial metabolites. The selective activity observed in this study also suggests specificity in the mode of action of these compounds, indicating potential for targeted antimicrobial applications. Overall, this research supports the concept that antagonistic endophytic bacteria from medicinal plants are valuable reservoirs of novel bioactive compounds. Further studies involving molecular identification, purification, and characterization of these metabolites, along with evaluation against a broader range of pathogens, are necessary to explore their potential in pharmaceutical and biotechnological applications.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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